

Delivery Performance, Delay Risk, and Logistics Efficiency Analysis in Global Supply Chain Operations

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ABSTRACT

Supply chain management has become one of the most important operational functions in modern businesses, especially functions in modern businesses, especially in global trade, e-commerce, and manufacturing industries. Efficient supply chain operations ensure that products are transported from suppliers to customers in the right quantity, at the right time, and at the lowest possible cost. However, many organizations continue to face challenges such as shipment delays, poor logistics coordination, inappropriate shipping mode selection, and regional delivery inefficiencies. These issues directly impact customer satisfaction, profitability, and brand reputation.

This research focuses on analysing global supply chain delivery performance and predicting late delivery risks using machine learning techniques. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was conducted to identify hidden trends and operational bottlenecks related to shipping mode, market efficiency, regional performance, customer segments, and order profitability. Data preprocessing techniques such as handling categorical features, feature engineering, and train-test data splitting were applied to prepare the dataset for model building.

A Random Forest Classifier was implemented to predict delayed deliveries based on shipment and transaction attributes. The model achieved an accuracy of 69.65%, with strong precision and acceptable recall performance. In addition to predictive modelling, an interactive Streamlit dashboard was developed to visualize logistics performance, monitor KPIs, and support business decision-making. The proposed system can help organizations proactively identify risky shipments, reduce delivery delays, improve operational planning, and enhance overall supply chain efficiency.

KEYWORDS: Supply Chain Analytics, Machine Learning, Random Forest, Delay Prediction, Logistics Efficiency, Streamlit Dashboard, Delivery Risk Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In today's highly competitive and technology-driven business environment, supply chain management plays a vital role in ensuring smooth movement of goods and services across different locations. A supply chain involves procurement, inventory management, warehousing, transportation, order fulfilment, and final customer delivery. Efficient execution of these operations directly influences customer satisfaction, organizational performance, and long-term profitability.

One of the major challenges faced by supply chain organizations is delayed deliveries. Shipment delays can occur due to several reasons such as poor transportation planning, traffic congestion, wrong shipping mode selection, regional infrastructure limitations, weather conditions, and lack of real-time

monitoring systems. Frequent delays lead to increased operational costs, customer complaints, refund requests, and reduced trust in the company.

With the rapid growth of e-commerce platforms and international trade networks, managing logistics operations manually has become increasingly difficult. Businesses now generate huge volumes of transactional and shipment-related data every day. This data contains valuable insights that can be used to optimize operations, predict risks, and improve delivery performance.

Machine learning and data analytics offer advanced solutions for solving logistics problems. Predictive models can learn patterns from historical shipment data and estimate whether a new shipment is likely to be delayed. Similarly, dashboards and visualization tools can help managers understand regional inefficiencies, compare shipping methods, and make faster decisions.

This research aims to develop a complete data-driven solution for global supply chain analytics using machine learning and interactive dashboards. The project focuses on delivery performance analysis, delay risk prediction, and logistics efficiency monitoring.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many organizations operating in supply chain environments face repeated challenges in maintaining on-time deliveries. Customers increasingly expect faster and more reliable shipping services. However, companies often struggle with poor shipment planning, regional bottlenecks, high logistics costs, and lack of predictive visibility.

Traditional logistics systems generally provide only descriptive reports after delays occur. They do not offer proactive mechanisms to predict risky shipments before delivery failure happens. As a result, businesses are unable to take preventive actions such as changing routes, upgrading shipping modes, reallocating resources, or notifying customers in advance.

Additionally, organizations may not clearly understand which regions consistently underperform, which shipping methods cause more delays, or which customer segments experience poor service levels. Without data-driven insights, management decisions become reactive rather than strategic.

Therefore, there is a strong need for an intelligent system that can:

- Analyse historical supply chain data
- Detect operational inefficiencies
- Predict late delivery risk in advance
- Visualize important KPIs through dashboards
- Support faster and smarter logistics decisions

DATASET DESCRIPTION

The dataset used in this project contains historical records of global supply chain transactions and delivery operations. It includes information related to orders, customers, shipping, regional markets, product pricing, and profitability. The dataset represents real-world logistics activities across multiple geographic regions.

Important columns used for analysis and modelling include:

Columns	Description
Customer Id	Unique identifier for each customer.
Customer Fname	Customer's first name.
Customer Lname	Customer's last name.
Customer Segment	Segment to which the customer belongs (e.g., Consumer, Corporate)
Customer City	City where the customer is located.
Customer State	State or region of the customer.
Customer Country	Country of the customer.
Customer Zipcode	Zip or postal code of the customer.
Product Name	Name of the product ordered.
Product price	Selling price of the product.
Category Id	Unique identifier for the product category.
Department Name	Name of the department responsible for the product.
Shipping Mode	Shipping method used for delivery (e.g., Standard, Express).
Order Region	Regional classification of the order.
Order State	State or province where the order was delivered.
Order City	City where the order was delivered.
Market	Global market region where the order belongs.
Type	Payment method used for the order (e.g., Debit, Credit).
Days for shipment (scheduled)	Planned or scheduled shipping duration in days.
Days for shipping (real)	Actual number of days taken to ship the order.
Delivery Status	Current delivery status of the order.
Sales	Total sales amount generated from the order.
Sales per customer	Total sales value generated by the customer.
Benefit per order	Net profit or benefit earned from a single order.
Order Item Discount	Discount amount applied to the order item.
Order Item Discount Rate	Discount rate applied to the product price.
Order Item Product Price	Original price of the product before discount.
Order Profit Per Order	Profit earned from the order after costs.
Late delivery risk (target column)	Indicator showing whether the delivery was late (1 = Yes, 0 = No).

EXPLORATORY DATA ANALYSIS(EDA)

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was performed to understand the dataset and identify important patterns related to delivery performance and delay risk. The analysis was carried out using the complete dataset to ensure reliable insights.

Initially, the distribution of delayed and on-time deliveries was analysed using the Late_delivery_risk column. It was observed that a significant portion of orders experienced delays, indicating the need for predictive modeling.

Shipping mode analysis showed that Standard Class shipments had a higher delay rate compared to faster modes such as First Class and Same Day delivery. This indicates that shipping method plays a crucial role in delivery performance.

Region-wise analysis was conducted by calculating the average delay gap for each Order Region. Certain regions consistently showed higher delays, highlighting possible logistical inefficiencies.

Market-wise analysis was also performed to compare logistics efficiency across different global markets. Variations in delay patterns were observed across markets such as Europe, Pacific Asia and LATAM.

Additionally, relationships between Sales, Order Quantity, and Benefit per order were analysed to understand their impact on delivery outcomes.

Overall, EDA helped in identifying key factors influencing late deliveries and guided feature selection for the machine learning model.

Key Performance Indicators

On-Time %	SLA Success %	Avg Delay	Late Risk %	Shipping Efficiency %	Regional Delay Index
18.7%	42.72%	0.57days	54.83%	60.23%	60.7%

Delay Risk Analysis Dashboard

Late Delivery Risk Distribution

Delay Gap Histogram

Average Delay Gap by Region

DATA PREPROCESSING

Data preprocessing was performed to convert the raw supply chain dataset into a clean and machine learning ready format. Initially, the dataset was checked for missing values, duplicate records, and unnecessary columns. Columns such as customer names, IDs, and detailed address fields were removed because they were not useful for prediction.

Categorical columns used in this project, including Shipping Mode, Order Region, Market, Customer Segment, and Type, were transformed into numerical format using One-Hot Encoding.

Numerical columns such as Days for shipment (scheduled), Order Item Quantity, Sales, Benefit per order, Order Item Discount, and Order Item Product Price were selected as input features for the model.

After preprocessing, the dataset was split into training and testing sets using train-test split method. The training data was used to build the Random Forest model, while the testing data was used for performance evaluation.

Overall, preprocessing helped improve data quality, remove irrelevant information, and prepare the dataset for accurate prediction of late delivery risk.

FEATURE ENGINEERING

Feature engineering was performed to create meaningful variables that improve model performance and business understanding.

Delay Gap

A new metric was created:

Delay Gap=Actual Shipping Days – Scheduled Shipping Days

This helped measure operational delay severity.

Logistics Efficiency

Efficiency indicators were derived using shipping performance and timing consistency.

Regional Risk Ranking

Regions were ranked based on historical average delay trends

Business-Oriented Feature Selection

Final features were selected based on domain relevance and predictive importance. Feature engineering increased analytical depth and improved model intelligence.

RANDOMFOREST MODEL

Random Forest Classifier was selected as the final machine learning model for this project. Random Forest is an ensemble learning algorithm that combines multiple decision trees to generate accurate and stable predictions.

Reasons for selecting Random Forest:

- Handles both categorical and numerical variables efficiently
- Reduces overfitting compared to single decision trees
- Works well on medium and large datasets
- Generates feature importance scores
- Provides robust performance with less tuning

The model was trained using shipment, customer, pricing, and operational attributes to classify whether an order would face late delivery risk.

MODEL EVALUATION

The model was evaluated using multiple classification metrics to understand predictive performance.

Final Results:

- Accuracy: 69.65%
- Precision: 84.21%
- Recall: 54.69%
- F1 Score: 66.31%
- ROC-AUC Score: 0.75

Interpretation:

- High precision indicates that predicted delays were often correct.
- Moderate recall shows scope for capturing more delayed shipments.
- Balanced F1 Score reflects overall acceptable model quality.
- ROC-AUC score of 0.75 indicate good class separation ability.

Confusion matrix analysis further confirmed that the model identified a significant number of delayed shipments while minimizing false alarms.

FEATURE IMPROTANCE

Feature importance analysis was performed using the Random Forest model to identify the most influential variables affecting late delivery prediction. The results indicated that operational features such as Shipping Mode, Days for shipment (scheduled), Order Region, and Market has the highest impact on predicting delays. These features directly relate to how shipments are planned and executed across different locations. Additionally, business-related variables such as Sales, Benefit per order, Order Item Quantity, Discount, and Product Price also contributed to the model, influence delivery outcomes, Overall, the analysis confirms that both logistics planning and transaction-level attributes play a significant role in determining whether a shipment will be delayed.

Feature Importance

USER INTERFACE(DASHBOARD)

An interactive dashboard was developed using Streamlit to present the analysis and prediction results in user-friendly manner. The dashboard includes multiple modules such as Overview, Delay Risk Analysis, Shipping Mode Comparison, Regional and Market Diagnostics, Prediction Module, and Model Insights. Users can explore key performance indicators, visualize delivery trends, and analyse regional and market efficiency through dynamic charts. The prediction module allows users to input shipment details and instantly determine whether there is a high risk of late delivery. The Model Insights section provides evaluation metrics, confusion matrix, and feature importance for better understanding

of model performance. Overall, the dashboard simplifies complex data into actionable insights, enabling better decision-making in supply chain operations.

CONCLUSION

This research presented a complete end-to-end supply chain analytics solution using machine learning and dashboard visualization. The project analysed logistics operations, identified hidden inefficiencies, and predicted late delivery risk using Random Forest Classifier.

The developed Streamlit dashboard further enhanced usability by converting model outputs into clear business insights. The solution can help modern organizations improve shipment reliability, customer satisfaction, and overall operational efficiency.

Machine learning combined with supply chain analytics has strong potential to transform logistics management into a proactive and intelligent system.

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